

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION IN SATU MARE FROM THE STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE ATTENDING THE TUC-N BRANCH

Author(s)*: Călin Ciprian OȚEL¹, Carmen Gabriela BĂCILĂ²
Position: Lecturer, PhD, Eng.¹, Lecturer, PhD, Eng.²
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca^{1,2}
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania^{1,2}
Email: calin.otel@mis.utcluj.ro¹, gabrielabacila34@yahoo.com²
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro>^{1,2}

Abstract

Purpose – The results acquired through the present research can help to increase the quality of the activities from the TUC-N branch from Satu Mare.

Methodology/approach – Within the research that took place through the events organized in the project "Specialists for Satu Mare", the survey was used as method and one questionnaire for the students was used as instrument.

Findings – Only a little more than half of the students who received the questionnaire really want to get actively involved in solving the existing problems at the branch, especially in terms of promoting the image of the branch/university and of organizing to ensure the conditions of study and less in those of scientific research.

Research limitations/implications – The questionnaires were submitted only to the subjects that were present at classes during the project development.

Practical implications – The recommendations stated through research can be applied in practice within the branch.

Originality/value – The project was the first of its kind within the TUC-N branch from Satu Mare so the research is innovative.

Key words: quality, higher education, students.

About higher education

There are discussions about the phenomenon of globalization for more than 40 years, especially in the economic sphere due to the expansion of the world trade. "The technological and information revolution and the opening of financial markets have helped to provide the means to spread globalization, and education must directly follow transformations and new demands in order to support future changes and vocational training"(Cosma, M., 2004).

In countries with a developed economy, "investments in knowledge (research and development, higher education, information technology) are growing at higher rates than investments in the economy"(Belostecinic, G., 2016) as contemporary society becomes more and more a society based on knowledge and information.

The most important element of the knowledge-based society is represented by the university as it is involved in three types of activities: education, research and technological innovation. Through education information is transmitted to people, new knowledge is created through research, and technological innovation translates into practice this knowledge.

Quality assurance in higher education is therefore vital and involves taking measures that will continually improve the quality of teaching, learning and research, in order to increase the competitiveness of the university, to develop skills for graduates to become more competitive in the labor market, and to provide them with the best chances of personal development(Avornic, Gh., 2009).

Improvement of the quality(Oțel, C.C., 2006) in higher education can be achieved in several directions regarding: educational process, increasing the quality level of the teaching staff, management of student activities, infrastructure, research, promotion of the faculties and international cooperation.

In this paper will be discussed some aspects regarding the improvement of the quality in the higher education which were mentioned by the respondents and that can be applied in the Satu Mare Branch of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca:

- Educational process - obtain the feedback from the students concerning the didactic activity through questionnaires on the university site regarding the way in which the didactic activity is carried out (way of teaching, overlapping of the taught knowledge, etc.);
- Management of student activities - improvement of the student practice by participating in different projects, organization of meetings between students and employers to facilitate the employment of the students from the final years, development of the psycho-pedagogical counseling center, organization of the student scientific circles and rewarding the best students, organization and counseling of the students for participation in professional competitions, supporting of the educational, cultural, sporting events for faculty students, facilitate communication with students, master students (at the level of secretariats at both faculty and departments);
- Infrastructure - modernization of the laboratories through the own-funds, projects and sponsorships, improvement of the IT and communications infrastructure in faculties (performing computers, wireless access, etc.) and endowment of libraries, redevelopment of common spaces in faculties (sanitary groups, installing double pane glass, etc.);
- Research - increasing the involvement of masters and PhD students in the research activities of faculty departments;
- Promotion of the faculties - actions to promote the study programs of faculties to attract the best high school graduates, through visits to high schools by the teams of teaching staff and students.

Results of the research

In the light of the answers provided by the students, they are interested in improving the activities carried out at the branch of the university from Satu Mare in a very large proportion, almost 97 percent (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Are you interested in improving the quality of the activities carried out at the TUC-N branch in Satu Mare?

However, not all those who have showed themselves to be interested in this aspect want to be involved that much. Thus, only 59 percent want much and very much to get involved in solving existing problems (Figure 2).

Figure 2. How much do you want to get involved in solving the problems of the branch/university?

They consider that students can best be involved in "promoting the branch/university image" (57 percent), "organizing to ensure the study conditions" (55 percent) and less in "scientific research" (33 percent). The question addressed to the students had four variants of answers, and several variants could be chosen (Figure 3).

V1 = promoting the branch/university image;
 V2 = organizing to ensure the study conditions;

V3 = scientific research;
 V4 = other: "ideas, proposals, suggestions for improving the study conditions".

Figure 3. In what activities do you think the students of the branch/university can be involved?

In order to increase students' employability, the respondents placed on the first two positions of their options: "increasing the chances of practice in companies" (23.7 percent) "job/ internship/research collaboration" (20.8 percent) and almost 28 percent did not respond (Figure 4).

G1: increasing the chances of practice in companies;
 G2: high standards/quality of education;
 G3: job/internship/research collaboration;

G4: visits to companies;
 G5: meeting between companies-university-students/job fair;
 G6: collaboration to promote students/increase the students confidence.

Figure 4. How do you think the university/TUC-N branch of Satu Mare can be involved in increasing the chances of employing students in the companies from Satu Mare?

Regarding the study conditions from the branch, 81.7 percent of the students appreciate the material basis as good, very good or excellent (Figure 5).

Figure 5. How do you assess the material basis of the TUC-N branch in Satu Mare?

Approximately 88 percent of the respondents consider that the documentary material of the branch library is good, very good or excellent (Figure 6).

Figure 6. How do you evaluate the endowment of the library with documentary material?

Among the endowments mentioned by the students as necessary it was mentioned by far "equipped laboratories" (36.6 percent) followed, in almost equal proportions, by "sports facilities – gym/sports ground, tennis table, basketball basket" (11.9 percent) and "functional computers" (11.4 percent) (Figure 7).

The questions from Figure 4 and Figure 7 were open-ended, so in order to interpret the results, the answers were grouped into six groups (G1-G6) for the first question (Figure 4) and seventeen groups (G1-G17) for the second question (Figure 7). One respondent could mention several aspects, so the answer could fit into several groups.

Communication with the branch secretariat proves to be good, very good or excellent, according to the students (99 percent) that answered this question (Figure 8).

- G0: satisfied;
- G1: library/books;
- G2: sports facilities – gym/sports ground, tennis table, basketball basket;
- G3: equipped laboratories;
- G4: place for practice;
- G5: bigger parking;
- G6: rooms for students;
- G7: functional computers;
- G8: reading room/studio;
- G9: kiosk in the branch yard/automatic for food and refreshments/canteen;
- G10: modern equipment;
- G11: internet/wireless;
- G12: smoking area;
- G13: auxiliary spaces – benches, rocking chair, place for dining, park, recreation center, toilet in block B;
- G14: endowments in classrooms – modern blackboards, video projectors;
- G15: more access ways in the courtyard/ suitable entrance for cars;
- G16: medical office/medical assistance;
- G17: xerox/printer for students.

Figure 7. What other endorsements do you consider necessary for students?

Figure 8. How do you appreciate the communication with the branch secretariat?

Asked what extracurricular activities should be developed for the students, they have chosen for the first three positions: "counseling – professional guidance" (54.4 percent), "communication/socialization" (50.5 percent) and "sports" (44 percent). The question addressed to the students had five variants of answers, and several variants could be chosen (Figure 9).

V1 = cultural;

V2 = sports;

V3 = communication/socialization;

V4 = counseling – professional guidance;

V5 = other:

"electronic sports", "development activities in electronics", "student organization".

Note: The respondent had the option to mark multiple variants.

Figure 9. What extracurricular activities should be developed for the branch students?

Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the undertaken research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- At the declarative level, 97 percent of the surveyed students are interested in improving the activities carried out at the university branch from Satu Mare, but only a little more than half (57 percent) really want to get involved in solving the problems of the branch.
- Students consider that the activities they can be involved in are "promoting the branch/university image" (57 percent), "organizing to ensure the study conditions" (55 percent) and less in "scientific research" (33 percent).
- 81.7 percent of the students appreciate the existing material basis, including the documentary material of the library (88 percent of students), but would like more "equipped laboratories" (36.6 percent), "sports facilities – gym/sports ground, tennis table, basketball basket"(11.9 percent) and "functional computers"(11.4 percent).
- Among the extracurricular activities that should be developed for students, they mentioned those of "counseling – professional guidance" (54.4 percent), "communication/socialization" (50.5 percent) and "sports" (44 percent).

According to the above-mentioned results the following recommendations can be made:

- To stimulate and encourage students to participate in existing scientific research projects between the local companies and team of the technical university branch.
- To allocate additional funds for a better endowed laboratories, redevelopment of existing sports facilities and purchasing more performant computers.
- To establish an office for "counseling – professional guidance" and "communication/socialization" to help students find the right job and integrate more easily into the labor market.

Acknowledgements

This paper focuses on the results obtained from the implementation of the project “*Specialists for Satu Mare*” funded by the Satu Mare Local Council through the “G.M. Zamfirescu” Cultural Centre of Satu Mare, and the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, contract No. 3/444/11.04.2016, project manager: Șef lucr.dr.ing. Călin Ciprian Oțel. We take this opportunity to thank all parties involved in the implementation of the project.

References

Avornic, Gh.,

2009

Rolul universității în societatea bazată pe cunoaștere, Revista națională de drept, Nr.10-12, https://ibn.idsi.md/sites/default/files/imag_file/Rolul%20universitatii%20in%20societatea%20bazata%20pe%20cunoastere.pdf, accessed on 22.03.2018

Belostecinic, G.,

2016

Globalization And Some Challenges For Higher Education, <http://www.toknowpress.net/ISBN/978-9975-3129-7-4/8-15.pdf>, accessed on 29.07.2020

Cosma, M.,

2004

Globalizarea și educația, Revista Academiei Forțelor Terestre, Anul IX / nr.2 (34), Trimestrul II – 2004, https://www.armyacademy.ro/reviste/2_2004/r5.pdf, accessed on 28.07.2020

Oțel, C.C.,

2006

Conceptul de calitate, Revista de Management și Inginerie Economică, volumul 5, nr. 2(18), Editura Todesco, Cluj-Napoca.

Oțel, C.C.,

2019

Reflecții asupra învățământului superior tehnic românesc din perspectiva trinomului student - cadru didactic – angajator / *Reflections on the Romanian technical higher education from the perspective of the trinomial student - teaching staff – employer*, Editura Tehnica-Info, Chișinău, Republica Moldova.